

ISic1021

I.Sicily inscription 1021

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 195 (197) + 5992

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. τελευτ[ησ][---]
2. νὸς διὰ[κονος]
3. ἀπὸ κ[αλανδ]
4. ὦν [Ἰου]
5. νί[ων ---]

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492648

EDCS 39102175

PHI 140499

Bibliography

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